

A Study on Customer Attitude towards online Banking Services of Banks with Special Reference to Thoothukudi District

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Abstract

Bank plays an important role in the economic development of a country. It is a financial institution that accepts deposits and channels those deposits into lending activities either directly or through capital markets. A bank connects customers which have capital deficits to those customers with capital surpluses. The banking industry in India is facing certain challenges i.e. challenges of quality service, customer satisfaction, customer retention, customer loyalty. Quality service plays a major role in achieving customer satisfaction and creating brand loyalty in banking sector.

The main objective of this research is to analyze the attitude of customer towards online banking services in Thoothukudi District. The present study based on both primary and secondary sources and the primary data were collected through Structure Questionnaire. Totally 300 customers were selected on the basis of convenient sampling for the study. The study may end with banks must focus on customer service with retention and relationship management, upgrade and offer integration and value added quality services. Technology is helping the banks to reduce transaction or maintains cost and improves operational efficiency of Indian banking sector.

Keywords: Online Banking, Internet, Customer, Attitude, Fund Transfer and Efficiency.

Introduction

Basically the banks and financial institutions are service – rendering organization. They render their valuable services to a large number of clients, who are spread all over the country. The Government of India, after independence had to focus on many areas among which one of the important tasks was economic development of the country. In this context, the Industrial policy resolution in 1948 focused on mixed economy, which played an active role in development of different sectors including banking and finance. A major step in this direction was the nationalization of banks in 1948. The Banking Regulation Act was enacted which empowered the Reserve Bank of India (RBI) to regulate, control and inspect the banks in India. In other words the Government of India nationalized banks in 1969 and later in 1980 in order to have better control over this sector. Government of India controls around 91% of the banking

business in India. In early 1990s, The Prime Minister of India P.V NarsimhaRao liberalized the sector by giving licenses to a small number of private banks, which came to be known as New Generation Tech-Savvy banks. There are ,Global Trust Bank (Now acquired by Oriental Bank of Commerce), UTI Bank (now re-named as Axis Bank), ICICI Bank and HDFC Bank. The banking sector in India constitutes Government banks, Private banks and Foreign banks.

Review of Literature

Muhammad Shakil Ahmad.,(2011) in his study entitled “E-Banking: A Case Study of Askari Commercial Bank Pakistan”, analysed the operational issues related to e-banking as well as customer’s perception on usage of e-banking a case study of Askari Bank, Pakistan. 40 staff members and four customers are selected as sample for this study. Both qualitative and quantitative methods are used to present the results. Descriptive statistics is applied to describe the demographic variables while for operational problems correlation was used. Finally cross case analysis present customers’ perception about e-banking practices. Analysis shows that customer is not ready to adopt new technology that why their satisfaction level with e-banking is low. Internet speed and government policies are not supportive for e-banking in Pakistan. Due to lack of trust on technology and low computer literacy rate, customer hesitates to adopt new technology. : In order to promote IT culture in Pakistan, government has to reduce the internet rate. to promote the benefits of e-banking on media so that more user get facilitated from e-banking services.

Dhurgham Ahmad, T and Mohammad Hariri.,(2012) in their study entitled “User Acceptance of Biometrics in E-banking to improve Security”, made an attempt to evaluate the use of biometrics in the online banking industry for user authentication so that the banking consumers primarily make use of online banking. The study adopted qualitative method of data collection whereby it revealed the user’s perceptions and their intention to use biometric in online banking for further authentication. The study also recommends the various factors influencing the implementation of biometrics in online banking.

Objectives of the Study

The following are the objectives of the present study:

1. To analyze the attitude of customer towards internet banking services in the study area.
2. To offer suggestions to improve the standard of online banking services, findings and conclusion.

Methodology and Research Design

The present study is based on both primary and secondary data. The required primary data were collected through structured questionnaires from customer. The required secondary data were collected through books, journal, magazine, unpublished office records, thesis, websites and the like.

There are totally 17 public sector banks available in Thoothukudi district. During the course of personal discussion with bank officials it is known that the majority of bank customers using e-banking services have been operating their bank account in urban and semi urban branches. Based on the performance of bank in terms of volume of transaction and operations five leading public sector banks were selected in the study area. Totally 300 customers were selected on the basis of convenient sampling for the study.

Results and Discussion

Online Banking in India

At present, Indian Banking Industry has grown rapidly in the midst of information technology revolution. People are beginning to see the convenience and benefits of e-banking. The entry of new banks in Indian banking industry has resulted in a paradigm shift in the base of banking in India. The number of individuals utilizing internet services has increased considerably.

Bank view internet banking as a powerful ‘value added’ tool to attract and retain new customers. Internet banking also helps to eliminate costly paper handling and teller interaction in an increasingly competitive banking environment. Internet banking enables a customer to perform through the bank’s website. This is also called virtual banking, net banking or anywhere banking. In India, the Indian customer is steadily moving towards internet banking. A number of banks have either adopted internet banking or they are on the threshold of adopting it. At present, internet banking services are available at limited branches and have to grow beyond metros to the semi-urban and rural areas to increase their online customer base. Banks in India are investing heavily to develop internet banking infrastructure and building an internet brand image. Internet penetration is growing and the profiles of the users banking are very attractive and customers between the 30-40 age groups are quite proficient in using this technology.

Table 1 SWOT Analysis of Internet Channel in Banking Sector

Strengths	Weaknesses
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Lowest cost per transaction • Minimum physical infrastructures • Round the clock availability • Convenience banking • Account integration for single relationship view • Waiting time eliminated • Information gateway 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • All transactions not possible • Slow adopters to internet banking • Lack of human interface • Poor penetration of internet in India
Opportunities	Threats
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Platform for cross selling • Value added services like ticket reservations • Virtual banking 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Security concerns • Lack of strong trust environment • Perceived notion that internet is not a safe place to conduct financial transactions • Not accessible to masses

Source: The Indian Banker Association

As per above table given above, one can find the strengths and opportunities of internet banking system. It is cost effective, helps to improve operational efficiency, connects the corporate with the customers, and has the ability to introduce new products to fulfill the customer’s needs while offering customer services anywhere, anytime with convenience. Internet banking has the ability to generate income, attract new customers to cross-sell, enhance image, and reduce customer attrition rate and combat competition. It is obvious that there are also some weaknesses and threats in using internet banking system. Security threats, lack of innovation in products, inadequate information about the product and network failure, are the major drawbacks involved in internet banking system.

Table 2 Online Banking user Level of Satisfaction

Particulars	Total	Mean score	Ranks
Online banking is safer and more secure	741	3.17	V
Online banking helps to review accounts balances easily	854	3.65	III
Online banking helps to transfer of funds & making payments	947	4.05	I
Online banking enables to buy and sell securities	603	2.58	IX
Online banking provides faster, easier and more reliable services	826	3.53	IV
Easily acquires information on products and services through e-banking	865	3.70	II
Diversity of services provided by e-banking	662	2.83	VI
Transaction fee of e-banking is cheap	593	2.53	X
Rules and statutory regulation on e-banking is effective	614	2.62	VIII
Programs / campaigns increase user's awareness	627	2.68	VII

Source: Primary data

The users believe that online banking help to “transfer of funds and making payments” at the highest ranking with a mean of 4.05. It is followed by e-banking easily “acquire information on products and services” with mean score of 3.70. Online banking review account balances and easily gets rank three with a mean score 3.65. Online banking provides faster, easier and more reliable services with a mean score of 3.53. It is followed by “ Online banking safer and secure” with a mean score 3.17 and total score 741. “Diversity services provided by e-banking” with a mean of 2.83 and total score 662. Program / campaign increase user's awareness is ranked as seven by respondents with a mean score 2.68 and total score 627. “Rules and statutory regulation on e-banking is effective” and “internet banking enables to buy and sell securities” are ranked as 8th and 9th with mean score of 2.62 and 2.58 respectively. “Transaction fee on e-banking is cheap” ranked next with mean score of 2.53. “lack of advertising about e-banking”. “e-banking provides help desk” and “e-banking knowledge among the public is high” have the lowest mean score of 2.26, 2.17 and 1.56 respectively. The overall analysis is reveals that most of them using online banking in order to helps customers to transfer of funds and making payments and Easily acquires information on products and services through e-banking.

Summary and Conclusion

- It is observed that the users believe that reveals that most of them using online banking in order to helps customers to transfer of funds and making payments and easily acquires information on products and services through online-banking.

Conclusion

The IT revolution had a great impact in the Indian banking system. The use of computers had led to introduction of online banking in India. The use of the modern innovation and computerization of the banking sector of India has increased many fold after the economic liberalization of 1991 as the country's banking sector has been exposed to the world's market. Online banking becomes a powerful weapon for improving customer satisfaction and in increasing operational efficiency. The banking industry also recognized that the online must be secure to achieve high level confidence with both customers and business. If banks have to retain their competitiveness, they must focus

on customer retention and relationship management, upgrade and offer integration and value added services. The study may end with banks must focus on customer service with retention and relationship management, upgrade and offer integration and value added quality services. Technology is helping the banks to reduce transaction or maintains cost and improves operational efficiency of Indian banking sector.

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